

ANGLO-MANIPURI WAR 1891

on newspaper front pages around the world

Wangam Somorjit

“The Manipuris attack was stubborn and determinedly made, and they pushed forwards in spite of the destructive fire with which they were received ... (they) fought gallantly for every foot of ground, the attack lasting three hours, during which some superb fighting was witnessed on both sides.”

—The New York Times, April 10, 1891

The Anglo-Manipuri War was not a local event that found no echo in the rest of the world. It is one of the most pernicious events of the world of the year 1891. The New Zealand newspaper *Star* in its retrospective column published on December 31, 1891 stated it as “*the worst incident*” of that year. The war convulsed the British Empire more deeply than any event since the Second Anglo-Afghan War (1878-1880). It is also the most discussed and debated event related to Manipur by the international communities. The war was fought in two distinct phases and last for one month and three days. In the first phase, the British treacherously attacked the royal palace of Manipur on the daybreak of March 24, 1891. They were defeated and were forced to retreat towards Cachar and Burma. The British representatives were tried in the court of Manipur, and they were executed by the public executioner for their crime

against the monarch. In the second phase, the British invaded Manipur from three directions. The fighting was not confined only to the valley of Manipur, but it spread up to the Naga Hills. In the battle of Mao, two Naga villages were razed to the ground by the British. Finally, the Manipuris were defeated in the battle of Khongjom. On April 27, 1891, the British captured the palace and the Union Jack unfurled there.

The New York Times in its April 2, 1891 issue reports

“the massacre of British native troops at Manipur is a result of what is apparently the most important revolt against the British power that has been made for many years.”

DEPOT LEGAL
Paris
22
1891

L'Univers illustré

JOURNAL HEBDOMADAIRE

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LES ÉVÉNEMENTS DE MANIPOUR. — LE RAJAH DE MANIPOUR ET SON FRÈRE LE SENAPPÜTTY.

Voir page 407.

King Surchandra (sitting), Crown-prince Kulachandra, Senapati Tikendrajit, Major Thangal and Major Balaram.

The London Mail refers to it as the most serious calamity that has befallen the British army in India since the Battle of Maiwand. The newspapers published in Australia and New-Zealand wrote it as

“the worst disaster of the kind which had happened since the gallant and gifted Cavagnari lost his life at the hand of the treacherous Afghans.”

The Brisbane Courier in its May 5, 1891 issue states, “...the Cabul revolt of 1879, when Sir Louis Cavagnari and other members of the British Mission were murdered in the British residency may, perhaps, be cited as a close parallel to the story of Manipur deceit and bloodshed.” Inspired by the event, the native newspapers in India also started attacking the British colonialism with “strongly seditious and treasonable languages.” One Persian paper writes it as the beginning of the general uprising against the foreign rule of the country. The proprietor, editor and manager of a Calcutta vernacular journal known as the *Bungobashi* were accused for attacking the British with provocative articles. In this way, newspapers worldwide reported the development of the war.

The 1891 event cannot be treated as the revolt or rebellion against the colonial master. The king of Manipur was an Asiatic power in alliance with the Queen of Britain. It is a war between two sovereign states over their conflicting viewpoints on diplomatic relations. The *Madras Mail* clearly gives the intention of the British invasion of Manipur:

[Manipur] is on the highway from India to Burma in the North-West Frontier [of Burma]. A road was constructed by the British in 1836 during the First Burmese War, which has since been kept in repair. That road will probably form the basis of operations for future development of road and rail with a view to bringing Northern Burma into touch with this country... it will seem to many impolitic to leave a dependent and subordinate Native State like Manipur to be a constant source of irritation and trouble

between two such important parts of the Empire as Burma and Assam, and, undoubtedly it will be unwise unless we can make sure of the loyalty of the chief...

On April 27, 1891, even though the British hoisted the Union Jack at the Palace of Manipur, perhaps, however, the real victory went to the Manipuris because of the fact that the court of Manipur had given capital punishment to the British officials for challenging the monarch. It was the custom of the country. The law book of the country *Loiyumba Shinyen* lays down “*Ningthousemba Panglabadi tumna hatlo*” (Liquidate all those who are involved in the dethroning the ruler). Here it would be sufficient to quote from the *Madras Mails*,

‘there are no more independent and haughty people anywhere than the Manipuris themselves.’

The British, who only believed in extraterritoriality, could not tolerate the capital punishment given to their representatives. Since ancient period the Government of Manipur exercised exclusive jurisdiction over all foreign nationals who entered its territory. For instance, in 1881, a scion of the Pong dynasty known by the name of Pong Raja was sentenced to death by the Manipur government for taking part in the rebellion against the monarch. The ‘defeated’ British frequently used the terms such as “Treachery” and “Rebellion.” They also propagated it as an act of barbarism by spreading many rumors. For instance, the *San Francisco Mail* and the European newspapers published a rumor as news reporting from a Rangoon correspondent of *Times* that the bodies of the British officers were cut into pieces and fed to dogs beyond the city wall. The *Brisbane Courier* in its April 14, 1891 issue also reports:

“... It is stated that Mr. Quinton, two officers, and a bugler were hacked to pieces by the insurgents, and their mutilated bodies were then thrown outside the walls ... and devoured by pariah dogs. Mr. Grimwood, British Resident at Manipur, and two officers were shot, and their bodies were treated in a similar manner.”

*Capture of of Crown Prince Tikendrajit, King Kulachandra, Thangal General and Senapati Angousana.
(Source: The Graphic, 1891)*

But the *New York Times* in its May 18, 1891 issue reveals:

The latest accounts of the Manipur massacre will excite the resentment of Anglo-Indians even more than the first accounts. It shows also that the revolt is a much more serious and threatening blow to British prestige than was at first supposed, for it appears that instead of being the result of a casual riot the murder of the English representatives was an act of the native Government, a quasi-judicial act, done in a perfectly open and deliberate way. The wrath of every Englishman in India must wax hot when he learns that the representatives of Great Britain were beheaded by the public executioner, in the presence of a great crowd, and as an act of defiance to the British Empire. The men immediately responsible for

the murder have been convicted by a military tribunal, but their execution will scarcely overcome the contempt for the British power that the massacre itself must have inspired in all the natives who witnessed it at the time or who have heard of it since.

After a careful examination of the origin of the War, most of the newspapers arrived at the conclusion that Mr. Quinton, the Chief-Commissioner of Assam, was guilty of treachery for his attempt to capture Crown-Prince Tikendrajit in an open *darbar* and treacherously attacking the palace of a sovereign state without proclamation of war. The Australian Newspaper *Adelaide* in its May 18, 1891 issue under the heading 'British official accused of treachery' states,

"Many of the British Newspapers denounce this contemplated treachery. They blame Mr. Quinton and also Lord Lansdowne, the

Governor-General of India, for agreeing to any such course of procedure.”

The Daily Argus News made a headline on April 10, 1891 in these words, “WHY QUINTON WAS KILLED? He Burned Helpless Manipur Women and Children.” *The New York Times* in its May 16, 1891 issue writes, “*The Manipur Blue Book establishes most decisively the fact that the Government is responsible for the Manipur disaster.*” Here one may recall the comment given by Sir J Nott that the Manipur disaster is parallel with the calamities and sufferings of the first Afghan war which were due to the meddling of the “political.” As a result of the debate in the House of Lords and the House of Commons of Britain Sir J. E. Gorst sent a communication to Lord Salisbury to the effect that the allusions left him no alternative but to resign his post as Under Secretary of the India Office. *The New York Times* in its June 23, 1891 issue published the news under the heading “... Sir J.E. Gorst resigns.” Now the British, who wanted to cover the treacherous move of

Mr. Quinton, attempted to divert the issue by criticizing the moral of Prince Tikendrajit. Many newspapers began to write about the personal life of Tikendrajit. For instance, the *Sydney Morning Herald*s in its May 14, 1891 issue states:

“The Commander-in-Chief, or ‘Senaputty,’ as he is called, Tependra Singh [Tikendrajit], has reasons of his own for hostility towards the English. In March, 1888, he had two men flogged in the most brutal way, and looked on while they were being tortured. The circumstances were reported to the Chief-Commissioner of Assam, who advised the Maharajah to dismiss his Commander-in-Chief. At first the Maharajah announced his intention of doing this; but his courage failed him, and the incident was allowed to pass without further notice.’

The Press.

FRIDAY MAY 15 1891

**THE MANIPUR
EXPEDITION.**[PER PRESS ASSOCIATION.]
Received May 14th, 10.30 a.m.CALCUTTA, May 13.
The Manipur leaders are being tried
by martial law.**The Press.**[PER PRESS ASSOCIATION.]
Received May 13th, 10.40 a.m.CALCUTTA, May 12.
The report that Senaputty had been
captured turns out to be untrue.
Affairs in Manipur are quiet.LONDON, May 12.
In the House of Lords, Lord Cross,
Secretary of State for India; denied
that the Government had offered blood
money for the regent's capture.**The Ashburton Guardian.****MANIPUR HONORS.**CALCUTTA, June 2.
A large number of decorations have
been bestowed on Lieutenant Grant's
battalion, in recognition of their
gallant behaviour after the massacre
at Manipur. Lieutenant Grant him-
self will be promoted.**THE NEW ZEALAND HERALD.****THE MANIPUR RISING.****NATIVES ENTRENCHED.**[Press Association.—Electric Telegraph.—Copyright.]
CALCUTTA, April 30.
The rebels in Manipur are reported to
be strongly entrenched at Thonal.**The Nelson Evening Mail.**

TUESDAY JUNE 18 1891

The Manipur Disaster.CALCUTTA, June 15.
It was the Senapate, or Commander-in-
Chief, who was sentenced to death for com-
plicity in the Manipur massacre, not the
Subraj, as previously telegraphed. The
trial of the latter has not yet been con-
cluded.**The Ashburton Guardian.**

TUESDAY, JUNE 23, 1891.

THE MANIPUR AFFAIR.CALCUTTA, June 22.
The Secretary of State for India has
sanctioned a pension of £300 a year to
Mrs Quinton, widow of the Commis-
sioner of Assam, who was killed at
Manipur.**The Evening Post****MARTIAL LAW IN MANIPUR.
TRIAL OF REBEL LEADERS.**[SPECIAL.]
(Received May 14, 10.40 a.m.)
CALCUTTA, 13th May.
The Manipur leaders are being tried by
martial law.**The Ashburton Guardian.**

TUESDAY, JUNE 16, 1891.

THE HEROINE OF MANIPURThe Princess of Wales is starting a
subscription for Mrs Grimwood in re-
cognition of her gallant conduct during
the retreat from Manipur.**The Star.****THE MANIPUR
DISASTER.**

[BY ELECTRIC TELEGRAPH.—COPYRIGHT.]

[SPECIAL TO PRESS ASSOCIATION.]

[Received April 7, at 10.45 a.m.]
CALCUTTA, APRIL 6.A despatch has been received from
Lieutenant Grant stating that he
believes himself to be the only
European left alive in Manipur. The
relieving forces are hurrying the
whole of the Ghoorka army in
Manipur to the fort captured at
Thonal by Lieutenant Grant.The Mironzai have risen, and com-
menced a general attack. A strong
punitive force is proceeding to Kohan
to repress them.**The Woodville Examiner.**

WAIKAWA ADVERTISER AND EAST COAST GAZETTE.

Execution of Manipur Leaders.CALCUTTA, August 14.
The Senapaei and Tangal General were
publicly handed to-day.**The New Zealand Herald.**

THURSDAY, MAY 14, 1891.

AFFAIRS QUIET.

[Press Association.—Electric Telegraph.—Copyright]

CALCUTTA, May 12.
The general of the Manipur troops and
the Minister of the Durbar has been
arrested.The report that Senaputty had been
captured turns out to be untrue.
Affairs in Manipur are quiet.

LONDON, May 12.

In the House of Lords, Lord Cross,
Secretary of State for India, denied
that the Government had offered blood
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money for the regent's capture.**The Nelson Evening Mail.**

COMMERCIAL AND GENERAL ADVERTISER.

THURSDAY AUGUST 13 1891

Rumour Contradicted.LONDON, August 12.
The Times states that the rumoured an-
nexation of Manipur by Great Britain is
improbable.**The Evening Star.****THE MANIPUR REVOLT.**[BY ELECTRIC TELEGRAPH.—COPYRIGHT.]
[PER PRESS ASSOCIATION.]CALCUTTA, MAY 16.
Despatches received respecting the
Manipur revolt show that Mr Quinton
intended arresting the chief Sonaputi in
open durbar, and leave the Regent on the
throne. Many newspapers denounced the
action as treacherous, and blame Mr quin-
ton and the Marquis of Lansdowne for it.
The papers also condemn the inadequate
force sent to Manipur.

The Auckland Star.

SICKNESS IN MANIPUR.

CALCUTTA, June 1.

There is much sickness in the Manipur expedition. Forty deaths are reported in a detachment of the 260 Rifles.

CALCUTTA, August 15.

The Viceroy of India has decided not to annex Manipur.

CALCUTTA, May 10.

The capture of the Maharajah of Manipur is expected daily.

The Bush Advocate

TAKAPAU, OSMONDVILLE, ROSEWOOD, MAKOTUKU, DANEVIRKE, AND WAINUI DISTRICT ADVERTISER.

THE EUROPEANS DESTROYED.

LIEUT. GRANT SOLE SURVIVOR.

(PER PRESS ASSOCIATION.)

CALCUTTA, April 6.

A despatch has been received from Lieut. Grant stating he believes himself to be the only European left alive in Manipur. Relieving forces are hurrying the whole of the Ghoorka army in Manipur to the fort captured at Thonal by Lieut. Grant.

The Ashburton Guardian.

CALCUTTA, July 6.

The Senapati, who was sentenced to death for complicity in the Manipur revolt, has been feigning madness, and attempted to commit suicide.

Marlborough Express.

AND WAIRAU BI-WEEKLY RECORDER.

THE INDIAN RISING.

(UNITED PRESS ASSOCIATION.)

CALCUTTA, May 12.

The General of the Manipur troops and Minister of the Durbar have been arrested.

THE ILLUSTRATED LONDON NEWS

OUR ILLUSTRATIONS.

THE MANIPUR EXPEDITION.

While the Imperial Government of India still deliberates, in its councils of State, on the treatment of the revolted Princes of Manipur and on the future political administration of that sequestered province, some interest yet belongs to the disastrous event of last March, the massacre of Mr. Quinton, Mr. Grimwood, Colonel Skene, and their companions, and to the brief campaign of Brigadier-General Graham, by which the British supreme authority was promptly restored. Our correspondent, Surgeon A. G. E. Newland, with the troops of the Burmese frontier, which entered Manipur from the south side, at Tummu, co-operating with the main force descending from Assam, has contributed views of the Maharajah's Palace, the

THE WESTERN GATEWAY OF THE PALACE AT MANIPUR.
FROM A PHOTOGRAPH BY SURGEON A. G. E. NEWLAND.

Durbar Hall, and the western gateway, where several of our countrymen were treacherously killed. Another of his photographs represents some of the Panthay mule-drivers and their beasts engaged in the transport service of the expedition.

THE DURBAR HALL AT MANIPUR.
FROM A PHOTOGRAPH BY SURGEON A. G. E. NEWLAND.

The *Launceston Examiner* in its May 25, 1891 issue writes:

“TIKENDRAJIT SINGH, the Commander-in-Chief, or Senapati of the Manipur rebels, is described as a ferocious savage. He has been known for some years as ‘the wanderer’ and was the prime mover in every species of revolt. Even during the time of Chundra Kirti Singh, his father, Koireng had acquired a bad name. Before Sura Chandra came to the throne, four years ago, Koireng was found guilty of an atrocious murder, and was exiled to Lake Loktak for a year by Colonel Johnston. More recently, he wreaked his vengeance upon two villagers for a fancied offence by piercing them on a machan [Bamboo frame] and lighting a fire below them. For half roasting these poor wretches Koireng was only fined fifty rupees, and had, we believed, to thank Mr. Grimwood for the leniency of his sentence.”

Thus a series of scandals about his private life broke on the front pages of all the papers.

After the conclusion of the War with the defeat of the Manipuris the newspapers began to publish articles on the trials of the Manipuri prisoners. The capture of Prince Tikendrajit was breaking news in British India, Europe, America,

Australia, Singapore and other South-East Asian countries. The news was published on May 26, 1891 under different headings such as ‘*Manipur War – Capture of the Senapati*’ ‘*Capture of the Manipuri Commander*’, etc. Tikendrajit, who pledged before that “*the British Government will get my corpse, perhaps, but never me alive*” attempted to commit suicide in his cell. *The Sydney Morning Herald* and *Timaru Herald* published the news in their July 10, 1891 issues under different headings.

After the trial, King Kullachadra, Prince Angou Sana, Prince Zilla and other ministers were deported to the Andaman Island. Prince Tikendrajit and General Thangal were hanged to death on August 13, 1891. *The Graphic* (London, Saturday, August 29, 1891, issue 1135) published the news under the heading “*The Manipur Rebels*” with the photographs of King Kulachandra, Crown-Prince Tikendrajit, General Thangal and Prince Angou Sana taken during their imprisonment. *The New York Times* published the news in its August 14, 1891 issue under the heading “*The Manipur Massacre avenged – Two of the leading instigators publicly executed.*” The newspaper condemned it with its statement,

“They were soldiers, but they were taken from their prison, led to a scaffold and there hanged like ordinary murderers.”

Others newspapers also strongly condemned it. *The Nelson Evening Mail* in its October 9, 1891 issue writes,

The Kohima Column

The First Brush with the Manipuris

“They were soldiers, yet not for them was the honour of a soldier’s death. They were not permitted to stand erect before a squad of soldiery and to hear the fatal command of ‘Ready, Aim, Fire!’.”

The Leader in its October 13, 1891 issue writes,

“The Manipuris regard hanging as a most disgraceful form of death, even in this manner of one of their princes has been given them a shock they are not slow to get over.”

Now the question of the annexation of Manipur was debated in the two Houses of Britain. It is worth to mention Sir Richard Temple’s statement, “...The loss of European life by murder and treachery is always most serious in India; in this case it is aggravated by the rank of the victims – the ruler of a province, the political agent, the military commander. The question still remains as to what shall be done with the State...” *The Graphic* (London, May 9, 1891, Issue 1119) writes:

The little State whose name has been on all English lips for the last fortnight, presents a somewhat thorny question to the Indian Government. What is to be done with Manipur now that, according to Eastern usages, it has forfeited all claim to independence? Sir J. Johnstone, who knows the country well and loves it, pleads forcibly

against the drastic process of annexation. Were that decreed, Manipur would gradually lose all its peculiar characteristics and picturesqueness, to become a mere replica of dozens of other Indian provinces.... annexation would wipe out at once and for ever all vestige of Manipur as a country per se.

Finally, the Viceroy of India had decided not to annex Manipur. However, the kingdom was degraded into a native state of British India.

The Anglo-Manipuri War was the bold example of how Manipur responded to the Western colonialism. Along with their search for minerals and discovery of tea, coal (in Manipuri, *Amuba-lang* as reported in the *Edinburgh New Philosophical Journal* in 1832), varnish and other natural resources in Manipur, the British had one main object since 1762. They projected a highway from India to Burma and China through Manipur, especially to control the petroleum and minerals trade of the mainland Southeast Asia. The report of the meeting of the directors of the Assam Tea Company held in March 1840 further clarifies their prospect “to establish a regular communication between China and Assam (500 Chinese were then employed as labourers in the Assam Tea Company), if possible, so that Chinese artisans may find their way across with facility, from Yunan, through the Burmese territory, into Manipur, and thence they can easily be passed into Assam.” As early as 1832 Major F.J. Grant had surveyed the road from Manipur Valley to

The Manipur Expedition from Shillong

Tamu. Article 2 of the agreement signed between Gambhir Singh and F.J Grant in 1832 was on the subject of the construction of “*the road commencing from the eastern bank of the Jeeree and continued via Kalanaga and Kowpoom, as far as the Valley of Munnipore.*” The construction of this highway was directly funded by the British. Their object became very clear after the Anglo-Manipur War. *The New York Times* in its April 23, 1891 issue wrote that, “*the real object of the British now is to make railway route through Manipur to Burmah permanently safe, and to do that not only the faction engaged in the late troubles but all the hill tribes of Manipur must be tranquilized.*”

One of the reasons which compelled the British to retreat from Manipur in the first phase of the War as reported in the newspapers around the world was the failure of ammunition to the fact that the sepoy of the 43rd Regiment has Martinis, while Mr. Quinton’s escort of the 42nd and 44th Goorkhas has Sniders. *The Stars* in its 7138 issue, April 16, 1891 reports, “.... *the reserve at the British Residency was only intended for Martini-Henri Rifles. On the arrival of Commissioner Quinton’s escort it was found that they were armed with Sniders, and, consequently, the reserve stock was of no use to them.*” In New Zealand the

Retreating to Silchar, The Residency garrison

The British Cantonments, Langthabal, Manipur

Manipur example became a warning as *The Stars* in its 7149 issue, April 28, 1891 wrote:

“There is for New Zealand a moral in the story. The Martini-Henry is the arm of the Indian Empire, and has been for years. But the Snider got to the country first and appears to have remained in use amongst the escorts of outlying residents in barbarous places. Quite right, too, for no doubt the people of those parts has nothing equal to the Snider. But a Snider is useless without a bullet. Ammunition was not forwarded to those places in the nick of the time; it was discovered that men armed with the Snider were no better than spears men; there being a great many more spears men opposed to them, they perished. In New Zealand we are changing our arms. At present Snider is our weapon. We shall have to take care that whatever our weapon we have ammunition for it. At reviews and exhibitions the wrong ammunition is occasionally

served out ever now. We have begun badly so we should take warning by this fearful example at [sic] Manipur.”

In the field of literature and art, western fiction writers were occasionally influenced by the major historical events in Manipur. In the beginning of 19th century an anonymous English writer inspired by Gambhir Singh's *Levy* and its expertise in the first Anglo-Burmese War (1824-26) published a short story on Manipuri protagonists entitled “*Elleelah and Kissore*” in the journal called *Bentley Miscellany*, formally edited by renowned English writer Charles Dickens, in 1851. Similarly at the end of 19th century, inspired by the Anglo-Manipuri War, a play entitled “*The Victoria Cross*” was staged at the Lyceum Theatre. It was written by Paul M. Potter. The *New York Times* in its August 26, 1894 issue reports, “*The story is based on the recent rising in the native State of Manipur, where Mrs. Grimwood was the sole survivor of the massacre. The play embraces events which have marked revolts in India from the days of the Sepoy mutiny, but its tone is said to be light, and it depicts the humorous, rather than the serious, side of life among the Himalayas.*” The renowned American actor E. H. Sothern

